

Supporting Information

Click Pt(IV)-carbohydrates pro-drugs for treatment of osteosarcoma

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NMR, HR-MS and HPLC

Compound 9

¹H NMR

¹³C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 10

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 17

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 18

¹H NMR

¹³C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 11

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 12

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 19

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Compound 20

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

HR-MS

Complex 1

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR

HR-MS

Complex 2

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR

HR-MS

Complex 3

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

¹⁹⁵Pt NMR

HR-MS

Complex 4

HPLC. Chromatograms of complex 4 in DMSO/HEPES (pH 6.8): a) $t = 0$ minutes; b) after one week at r.t.

^1H NMR

^{13}C NMR

COSY

HSQC

HMBC

^{195}Pt NMR

-087/1536

HR-MS

Dose-response curves used to generate IC_{50} for cisplatin and complexes **1-4** inhibitor activity on viability of SAOS-2 (1), U-2 OS (2) and MG63 (3) cell lines. Log[concentration] in μM and the normalized response (%) of survival fraction of cells are reported on X and Y axes, respectively. 50% survival cells is highlighted in Y dotted line. For each cell line, curves interpolation with 50% survival cells correspond to LogIC_{50} of each drug. Data are reported in the graph as mean \pm standard deviation. For IC_{50} values see table 1.